

ISic3640

I.Sicily inscription 3640

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object

funerary altar

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

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Autopsy

2015.01.13

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)**Place of origin (modern)**

Ispica

Provenance

Contrada Carrubba (36.760765, 14.965952), proprieta Fidelio, at km 8
(36.741943, 14.985649) on the Ispica-Pachino road

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Ragusa, Museo Archeologico
Ibleo

Physical Description**Dimensions**

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout**Execution**

Engraved

Letter Forms**Letter heights:**

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text**Apparatus****Translation****Commentary****Digital identifiers:**

TM 645706

EDCS 70900998

Bibliography

Manganaro, G. 1965. Ricerche di antichità e di epigrafia siceliote. *Archeologia Classica*. 17: 183-210. At 199 tav.70.3

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